

Graduates', university lecturers' and employers' perceptions towards employability skills

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Purpose- The purpose of the study was to explore employability skills that employers, university lecturers and graduates value to bring to the workplace when graduates are applying for entry-level graduate jobs in the field of computer science in Sri Lanka.

Design/methodology/approach- Three samples were selected for this exploratory study, namely, graduates, employers and university lecturers. Three self-administered survey questionnaires were developed targeting the three groups. In addition to descriptive statistics, paired sample t-test, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and correlation analysis were used for the data analysis.

Findings- The findings led to suggest that there are differences in the priorities given for employability skills by the four groups- male graduates, female graduates, employers and university lecturers. Further, the findings suggest that employability skills are influenced by the gender of the graduates. Overall, the findings of the study could be used to assist in universities, graduates, employers, and career advisors to apply strategic decisions in managing graduates' careers.

Originality/value- Although a considerable amount of the literature addresses employability skills, much of the information is theoretical in nature and offers policy recommendations and prescriptive advice. Further, a majority of the research studies has primarily examined the experiences of a particular higher educational institute where remedial actions were taken to impart employability skills. This article presents findings of a survey that investigated and compared employability skills that employers, university lecturers and graduates value to bring to the workplace when graduates are applying for entry-level graduate jobs.

Keyword(s): Employability; Employability skills; Graduates, Sri Lanka.

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

The term employability is used to refer to the ability of an individual to gain employment appropriate to his/her educational standard (Dearing, 1997). The literature suggests three key elements of employability, i.e., the ability to gain initial employment, the ability to maintain

employment and make transitions between jobs and roles within the same organisation to meet new job requirements, and the ability to obtain new employment, if required, by being independent in the labour market and able to manage employment transitions between organisations (Hillage and Pollard, 1999). Employability of an individual depends upon assets in terms of knowledge, skills and attitudes; the way these assets are used and deployed; the presentation of assets to potential employers, and context within which the individual works (for example labour market and personal circumstances) (Hillage and Pollard, 1998). In this regard, the literature suggests that there is a gap between skill requirements for entry-level graduate employment and skill levels of entry-level graduate job applicants (see Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2003; Davies, 2000; Finn, 2000; Lindsay, 2002; National Science Foundation of Sri Lanka [NSF], n.d.; Ranasinghe, 1992). A good supply of skilled employable graduates is essential for national, economic and social well-being and the failure to equip young people with employability skills has far-reaching consequences (see Bhaerman and Spill, 1988; Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2003; Cotton, 1993; NSF, n.d.). It is also argued that providing young people with skills for employability is an ethical responsibility (Bhaerman and Spill, 1988).

For several reasons, research into graduate employability skills is important. First, although a considerable amount of the literature addresses employability skills, much of the information is theoretical in nature and offers policy recommendations and prescriptive advice (e.g. Ball, 2003; Cotton, 1993; Davies, 2000; Ranasinghe, 1992; Raybould and Sheedy, 2005). Further, a majority of the research studies primarily examined the experiences of a particular higher educational institute where remedial actions were taken to impart employability skills (e.g. Fallows and Steven, 2000). While case studies provide insights into the status of employability skills and the impact of remedial actions in specific situations, the lack of generalisability has hampered the development of an overarching framework for

interpreting and framing research applicable across organisations (see Nabi and Bagley, 1998). Specifically, a majority of the studies failed to include statistical treatment of data. This creates a limitation in comparing the prevailing situation across academic institutions and countries. For instance, there is no agreement over whether there is a skill gap or how big it is if it exists (see Dearing, 1997). Hence, the need for rethinking the methodologies that are being applied in contemporary employability research has to be highlighted.

Second, there is increasing evidence for the need for information about graduates' transition to work, particularly in the crucial period shortly after graduation, and graduates' early careers (see Ball, 2003; Connor and Shaw, 2008; Holden and Hamblett, 2007). As Ball (2003, p8) points out "the notion of a 'graduate level' job and a linear career path are no longer realistic expectations for the 21st century graduate in any subject of study, as graduates engage with a diversity of work, many working in smaller enterprises, or on a freelance basis". Hence, higher educational institutions need to identify demanding different working patterns that graduates might engage in and ensure that they possess employability skills that employers prefer them to possess. However, it is very difficult to find empirical studies that investigated and compared employability skills that employers, university lecturers and graduates value to bring to the workplace when graduates are applying for entry-level graduate jobs. And also studies that compared the level of skills possessed by graduates by the time of applying for the first job (graduate responses) and the level of skills expected by employers when selecting for entry-level graduate jobs (employer responses). Hence, there is a clear need for such studies. The present study makes an attempt to fill this gap.

Third, it is important to explore how gender differences of graduates influence them in quipping themselves with employability skills for entry-level employment (Nabi and Bagley, 1998). However, as noted earlier, it is very rare to find previous empirical studies that investigated gender differences in the assessment of different employability skills and

measures that they have taken to enhance their skill levels (see Nabi and Bagley, 1998). For instance, Nabi and Bagley (1998) in a survey conducted in the University of Central Lancashire, UK, found differences between male and female responses in terms of importance and quality of employability skills. In this regard, Sri Lanka is trying to promote gender equality in terms of increasing women's participation in the workforce and in terms of the range of jobs open to them (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 1998). Yet, the tracer studies of science and technology graduates (1998-2002) conducted by NSF of Sri Lanka found that the percentage of unemployed graduates in their sample was 14.6 per cent; among unemployed graduates, the majority were females (64.1%), compared to males (35.9%) (NSF, n.d.).

Fourth, this study is conducted on computer science graduates and it is rare to find prior research studies on computer science graduates in any context. The software and computer services sector is currently one of the fastest growing sectors. The literature identifies software and computer services as a creative industry that has its origin in individual creativity, skill and talent, which have a potential for wealth and job creation through the generation and exploitation of intellectual property (see Department for Culture, Media and Sport, UK [DCMS], 2001). The contribution creative professionals make to social, cultural and economic life and the need for a co-ordinated strategy for supporting the growth of creative industries has been recognised (see Ball, 2003; DCMS, 2001). Further, specific literature on the IT industry in Sri Lanka as well as in India highlight that there are skill gaps in people entering the IT labour force every year (Learning Initiatives on Reform for Network Economies in Asia [LIRNEasia], 2006; Raman *et al.*, 2007). The study of LIRNEasia (2006) reveals that almost all firms in their study sample (95%) invest in training of newly hired employees to meet skill shortfalls. Furthermore, LIRNEasia (2006) and the Information and Communication Technology Agency of Sri Lanka (ICTA) (2005, 2007) highlight the importance of improving the supply of skilled personnel as a priority area that requires

immediate attention for the competitiveness and growth of this important sector. However, the employability skills of computer science graduates in Sri Lanka is an under-researched area.

Finally, the knowledge that has been accumulated through research efforts concerning graduate employability and employability skills has been confined to the West. It is very difficult to find research studies conducted in other parts of the world, especially in South Asia. Yet, the South Asian literature highlights that despite the large number of people entering the labour force every year there is a dissatisfaction with the supply of skilled personnel, who are low on quality and relevance (see LIRNEasia, 2006; Raman *et al.*, 2007; ICTA, 2007). Although a few published materials are available on employability and employability skills of graduates in Sri Lanka they offer policy recommendations and fail to include any proper statistical treatment of data (see NSF, n.d.; Ranasinghe, 1992).

In the above context, this exploratory study was conducted to expand the understanding of employability skills of computer science graduates in Sri Lanka by exploring the perceptions of computer science graduates, employers and university lecturers. The specific aims of the paper are: 1) to explore the skills that employers, university lecturers and graduates value to bring to the workplace when graduates are applying for the entry-level graduate jobs; 2) to explore whether there are any employability skill gaps in graduates; 3) to explore measures taken by employers, universities, and graduates to impart graduate employability skills. Though the study is exploratory in nature it is expected that the findings of the research presented in this article will provide new insights into graduate employability skills in Sri Lanka. The research setting is both progressive and international in nature and the paper explores a timely issue while maintaining an international perspective of the Sri Lankan context situated in the global environment. Consistent with the objectives, in the next section, relevant literature is briefly reviewed. This is followed by the methodology adopted.

Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. The paper concludes with a discussion on the limitations of the study and areas for future research.

Literature review

Employability skills

The term employability is used to mean a set of achievements that comprise skills, understanding and personal attributes that make an individual more likely to secure and be successful in his/her chosen occupation to the benefit of him/herself, the workforce, the community and the economy (Yorke and Knight, 2004). The literature suggests two aspects of employability as subject skills and transferable skills. Transferable skills refer to certain personal abilities of an individual, which can be taken from one job role to another, used within any profession and at any stage of his/her career while subject skills are more relevant to ones career (Cox and King, 2006). Students usually leave university with a good appreciation of their chosen fields as they have studied those intensively during the degree programme (Cottrell, 2003). However, in today's challenging business environment the possession of subject skills alone is no longer sufficient for a new graduate in meeting employer requirements; increasingly it is necessary for them to gain transferable skills which will enhance their prospects of employment (see Cox and King, 2006; Fallows and Stevan, 2000; Harvey *et al.*, 1997; Warn and Tranter, 2001). Therefore, Buck and Barrick (1987) state that employability skills are attributes of employees, other than technical competence, that make them an asset to an employer. However, Atkins (1999) suggests that there is no reason why employers should have a common set of skills that they require graduates to develop as this may vary with the region, the size of business, and the market orientation of the business. Over the recent years there is a consensus that employability skills of Sri Lankan graduates should be developed during their university education (NSF, n.d.). The

World Bank funded project “improving relevance and quality of undergraduate education (IRQUE)” was recently implemented to enhance the undergraduate education of the country (Ministry of Tertiary Education and Training, 2004).

The idea of employability skills as transferable skills has been reinforced by changes in employment patterns. On the one hand, when firms down-size the workforce they require people to attend to a wider range of tasks than hitherto, as well as to be more flexible in meeting the needs of customers (Fallows and Stevan, 2000). On the other hand, the world of employment is changing rapidly. Permanence is no longer a significant feature: traditional career paths have disappeared and new technologies have made established practice and experience irrelevant (Clarke, 2008; Fallows and Stevan, 2000). Hence, increasingly, graduate attributes are more important than the specific occupational skills (see Busse 1992; Cotton, 1993; Lees, 2002; LIRNEasia, 2006; Young 1986). For some employers, subjects studied during the degree programme are not as important as the graduates’ ability to handle complex information and communicate it effectively (see Knight and Yorke, 2002b; LIRNEasia, 2006). According to Cotton (1993), employability skills are not merely attributes that employers desire in prospective employees; many employers require applicants to have these skills in order to be seriously considered for employment.

The literature also reveals that graduate applicants seeking their first career jobs do not possess employability skills which employers require (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2003; Cotton, 1993; Davies, 2000; NSF, n.d.). It is said that the mismatch between supply and demand conditions for graduate employment in Sri Lanka reflects a supply driven higher education system with little relevance to prospective employers in the private sector, which has shut off appropriate employment opportunities for a substantial number of graduates (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2003; Ranasinghe, 1992). Further, the NSF of Sri Lanka (NSF, n.d.) identified one of the obstacles faced by science and technology graduates who were in

temporary employment and failed to obtain suitable permanent employment, as the lack of generic skills, which could be removed through necessary curriculum changes in the university education and by getting the involvement of the industry. In this regard, Swiatek (2000) found that there are differences in the importance given to employability skills by graduates and employers according to their perceptions.

Methods for imparting skills

Several studies recommended remedial actions for imparting graduate employability skills (such as Bedingfield, 2005; Dearing, 1997; Cotton, 1993; Hayman and Lorman, 2004; McDermott *et al.*, 2006; Ministry of Tertiary Education and Training, 2004; NSF, n.d.; Pool and Sewell, 2007). Harvey (2000) advocates the view that the primary role of higher education is to train students by enhancing their knowledge, skills, attitudes and abilities, and to empower them as lifelong critical and reflective learners. Similarly, several other studies also indicate that employability skills are very amenable to be taught during the undergraduate degree programme (such as Cotton, 1993; Cox and King, 2006; NSF, n.d.; Pool and Sewell, 2007; Rae, 2007; Zinser, 2003). It is identified that employability skills are most likely to be taught and learned when the acquisition of them is explicitly stated along with other program goals in academic curricula across all disciplines as opposed to creating a separate “employability course” (Fallows and Steven, 2000). This places employability skill development on the same level as subject skills, thereby communicating to students that they are important and need to be learned (Cotton, 1993; Zinser, 2003). However, exactly where in the curriculum these skills should be included has been largely a local decision (Zinser, 2003).

Several studies propose that universities should get employers involved in the design, delivery and assessment of courses (such as Cox and King, 2006; Hegarty and Johnston,

2008; NSF, n.d.) while some other studies suggest that universities need to demonstrate that their programmes of study comply with requirements for benchmarking, professional and statutory bodies, level descriptors, and academic review (such as Knight and Yorke, 2002a). Stephens and Hamblin (2006) and Brine and Feather (2002, 2003) suggest that students can document skills using personal development portfolios. Some others propose introducing workshop style courses that have additional benefits of networking and sharing of good practices (such as Raybould and Sheedy, 2005).

However, as there are difficulties in the skill transfer process, a strong emphasis upon practical application of the learned skills in a variety of contexts has been particularly well received by both graduates and employers (see Atkins, 1999; Knight and Yorke, 2002b; Lees, 2002; Raybould and Sheedy, 2005). Therefore, it is difficult to rely on a single strategy for the enhancement of employability skills; a mix of learning and development approaches would be beneficial.

Methodology

Sample selection

The study is confined to exploring employability skills of computer science graduates who have passed out from Sri Lankan universities. Three samples were selected for this exploratory study, namely, graduates, employers and university lecturers. Sample selection was conducted in three stages. The first stage was selecting a random sample of employers. Software development firms registered under Sri Lanka Association for Software Industry was taken into account to identify the employers. The second stage was the selection of graduates who are employed in these randomly selected firms. In selecting a random sample of graduates, computer science graduates who passed out from the universities less than 12 months previously, who are in their first employment and have 6 months to 1 year of work

experience in their first employment, were selected from those firms. As the third stage, from the graduates, the universities from which they passed out were identified in order to contact the university lecturers. This method of identifying respondents to represent the three groups and data collection consumed considerable time and effort. As detailed in the selection on “measures” three questionnaires were developed targeting the three groups.

The employers’ sample consisted of 26 employers. The average number of graduates employed by these firms during the last two years was 5 and the average number of graduates employed by these firms at the time of the survey was 10. Graduates’ sample consisted of 54 graduates. The mean age of the respondents was 27 years; 68 per cent of the sample was male. The graduates had passed out from 6 Sri Lankan universities and obtained general or special degrees in computer science such as B.Sc. in Computer Science and Engineering, B.Sc. in Computer Science, B.Sc. in Information Technology, and B.Sc. in Statistics and Computer Science. The sample of university lecturers consisted of 22 university lecturers from the six universities who undertook lectures for these graduates.

Measures

To achieve the purpose of the study, the identification of relevant skills formed the foundation. The graduate employability skills identified by different researchers vary considerably in the way they are organized (e.g. Dearing, 1997; Cotton, 1993; Coopers and Lybrand, 1998; Knight and Yorke, 2002a, 2002b, 2003; Lees, 2002; Zinser, 2003). Several studies identified that employers prefer graduates to possess an array of basic, higher-order, and affective skills when applying for entry-level graduate jobs (e.g. Buck and Barrick 1987; Busse, 1992; Cotton, 1993; Young 1986). For the study, Cotton’s (1993) categorization of basic skills, higher-order thinking skills, and affective skills and traits was used. Cotton (1993) identified oral communication, reading, basic arithmetic, and writing as basic skills;

problem solving, learning skills, creative and innovative thinking, and decision making as higher order thinking skills; positive attitude towards work, punctuality, self confidence, working as a team member, responsibility/dependability, ability to work without supervision, and adaptability/flexibility as affective skills and traits. These skills were defined simply, as a headline plus a few sample behaviours as in Yorke and Knight (2004).

The self-administered survey questionnaire was chosen as the mode for data collection; three self-administered survey questionnaires were developed targeting the three groups. A self- evaluation method of skills was used for graduates as it plays an increasingly prominent role in education and training field (see Hayes *et al.*, 2000). All questions in the three questionnaires were on a five point Likert scale (5=Very High, 4=High, 3=Average, 2=Low, 1=very low). Three questionnaires were piloted prior to distribution. The following questions were asked from graduates:

- The level of importance given to each skill during the undergraduate degree programme;
- The level of each skill possessed by the time of applying for the first job;
- The level of each skill perceived as ideal to be possessed by the time of applying for the first job;
- Measures taken to impart and/or to provide evidence of the possession of skills to employers- A range of options derived from the literature was listed. The option “other” was also added to the list to state any other measures used which were not offered by the questionnaire.

The following questions were asked from employers:

- The level of importance given to each skill when selecting graduates for entry-level graduate jobs;

- The level of each skill expected to be possessed by graduates when selecting for entry-level graduate jobs;
- Measures taken to impart skills in graduates after hiring for jobs- A range of options derived from the literature was listed. The option “other” was also added to the list.

The following questions were asked from university lecturers:

- The level of importance given to each skill during the undergraduate degree programme;
- Measures taken during the undergraduate degree programme to impart skills in students- A range of options derived from the literature was listed. The option “other” was also added to the list.

Data analysis was carried out by using the software package for social sciences (SPSS). In addition to descriptive statistics, paired sample t-test, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and correlation analysis were used for the data analysis.

Results

Table I shows the most important employability skills as identified by male graduates, female graduates, employers and university lecturers. Problem solving, self confidence, and working as a team member were identified as important by all four groups. Learning skills were identified as important by male graduates, female graduates and employers while a positive attitude towards work was identified as important by female graduates, employers and university lecturers. Creative and innovative thinking was identified as important only by male graduates while oral communication was identified as important only by university lecturers.

Insert Table I

The differences in the importance given to each employability skill by the four groups were analysed using ANOVA. The results are shown in Table II. There are significant differences in the importance given to learning skills ($p < 0.01$) and self confidence ($p < 0.05$). The analysis of Least Significant Differences (LSD) showed significant differences in the importance given to learning skills between male graduates and university lecturers ($p < 0.01$), between male and female graduates ($p < 0.05$), between female graduates and employers ($p < 0.01$), between female graduates and university lecturers ($p < 0.001$), and between university lecturers and employers ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, the analysis of LSD showed significant differences in the importance given to self confidence between female graduates and employers ($p < 0.05$) and between female graduates and university lecturers ($p < 0.05$) (the results of LSD are not shown in a table).

Insert Table II

The correlations among employability skills and gender are shown in Table III. Gender correlates significantly with learning skills and self confidence. Female graduates demonstrate a comparatively high level of self confidence and learning skills compared to male graduates. Results shown in Table III support the results shown in Table II.

Insert Table III

Skill gaps of graduates were identified at two levels. First, paired sample t-test was performed to explore differences between the level of skills possessed by graduates (graduate responses) and the level that they perceived as ideal to be possessed (graduate responses) by the time of applying for the first job. The results of this analysis are shown in Table IV. The differences in skill levels are significant for the majority of the skills for the two groups- male graduates and female graduates. For example, reading skills possessed by male graduates is below the level that they perceived as ideal to be possessed by the time of applying for the first job, and for male graduates this difference is significant ($p < 0.001$). However, such a significant difference does not exist for female graduates between the level of reading skills possessed and ideal to be possessed.

Insert Table IV

Second, the level of skills possessed by graduates by the time of applying for the first job (graduate responses) and the level of skills expected by employers when selecting for entry-level graduate jobs (employer responses) were compared. The results of this analysis are shown in Table V. Problem solving skills showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$). The analysis of LSD showed a significant difference between the level of problem solving skills possessed by both male and female graduates and employers' level of expectation ($p < 0.05$). It is apparent from Table V that employers' level of expectation is comparatively higher than the level possessed by both male and female graduates.

Insert Table V

Table VI shows the measures taken by graduates to impart and/or to provide the evidence of possession of skills to employers. The majority of female graduates rely on university job fairs while male graduates tend to rely on properly prepared CVs.

Insert Table VI

Table VII shows the measures taken by universities to impart skills in students during the undergraduate degree programme and measures taken by employers to impart skills after hiring for jobs.

Insert Table VII

Discussion and Conclusions

The study investigated and compared employability skills that employers, university lecturers and graduates value to bring to the workplace when graduates are applying for entry-level graduate jobs in the field of computer science in Sri Lanka. Widely recognised graduate employability skills that were mainly drawn from the earlier reviewed literature were explored in this study. The findings reveal that graduates prefer to have these skills in them and that the university lecturers and employers prefer graduates to possess these skills though there are some differences in their preferences. Overall, all the groups ranked problem solving, self confidence, and team work as the most important employability skills.

However, the findings suggest that there are differences in the priority given for the employability skill “learning” by the four groups- male graduates, female graduates, employers and university lecturers. These differences could have implications in placing graduates in appropriate employment and would increase the employers’ costs of training newly hired graduates. With regard to prior research, Swiatek (2000) also found that there are differences in the importance given to employability skills by graduates and employers according to their perceptions in the Australian context. Further, Nabi and Bagley (1998) found that that there are differences in the importance given to employability skills by male and female graduates in the UK context.

The findings of this study also suggest that employability skills could be influenced by gender. The nature of the sample selected led to assume that male and female graduates do not drastically differ in having equal education, employment, and equal chances to apply skills to appropriate work challenges and so on. However, the results suggest that male and female graduates differ in the extent to which they emphasize employability skills during their undergraduate degree programmes and their perceived levels of possession of these skills. Females have given a higher importance to all the employability skills except oral communication skills than male graduates. In this regard, Nabi and Bagley (1998) also identified that females tended to rate most of the skills as more important than males. Further, it was found in the current study that gender correlates significantly with “learning skills” and “self confidence”; female graduates demonstrate a comparatively high level of self confidence and learning skills compared to male graduates. On the one hand, it would be fascinating to investigate the reasons behind these differences in perceptions in future studies. On the other hand, an individual could undertake a needs analysis and could develop a plan to assist in skill development. In this regard, the most effective method(s) of imparting

skills could differ by the gender of the individual, which would also be fascinating to explore in future studies.

Another interesting finding of the current study is that both female and male graduates tend to rate the possession of a particular skill less than the level that they perceived as ideal to be possessed by the time of applying for the first job, except for basic arithmetic. Nabi and Bagley (1998) also identified that graduates tend to rate the importance of a particular skill more highly than their own ability in that skill. According to Nabi and Bagley (1998) this would mean deficiencies in the quality of their own skills. Hence, there is a need of improving the quality of transferable skills provided (Nabi and Bagley, 1998).

In the study, the level of skills possessed by graduates by the time of applying for the first job and the level of skills expected by employers when selecting for entry-level graduate jobs were compared. Though extant literature suggest that there are gaps between skill requirements for entry-level graduate employment and skill levels of entry-level graduate job applicants (e.g. Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2003; Davies, 2000; Lindsay, 2002; NSF, n.d), we only identified a skill gap in problem solving skills ($p < 0.05$), where employers' expectation is significantly higher than the level possessed by graduates. This may be because our study sample is confined to a specific field of undergraduate study catering mainly for an industry which has emerged in the country very recently.

The extant literature (such as Ball, 2003; Fallows and Stevan, 2000) suggests that one of the trends has been the rising expectations among employers of newly recruited graduates: not only graduates are expected to make a significant contribution to their organisations from almost the first day of employment, but they have to take responsibility for their careers. Further, there is evidence (see Ball, 2003) that graduates joining creative industries have to adapt, change direction and offer flexible services, for many without the benefit of the employers' involvement to foster their development. In other words, the

employment market requires graduates to be equipped with a range of skills in addition to their academic success. However, on the one hand, the extant literature suggests that graduates tend not to feel confident about the skills they have and find it difficult to recognise important employability skills and how they might be useful in the workplace (see Ball, 2003). On the other hand, higher education institutions could not be expected to provide undergraduates with a complete and comprehensive skill-base in preparing for future employment (see Nabi and Bagley, 1998). Therefore, one of the challenges for graduates is managing their relationship with work and with career and personal development. In this regard, extant literature (e.g. Nabi and Bagley, 1998) highlights the importance of helping graduates to acquire a broad range of employability skills regardless of their particular degree discipline, as those would be needed by employers in future. In this context, the findings reveal the sort of skills that employers' value graduates to bring to the workplace when applying for entry-level graduate jobs. Therefore, graduates could assess their skill levels along with employers' priorities well in advance of getting to the stage of applying for jobs and they could place emphasis upon skill development based around employers' priorities. In this regard, the most effective method(s) of imparting skills could also differ by gender of the individual, which would also be fascinating to investigate in future studies.

With regard to the measures taken by universities to impart graduate employability skills, curriculum revisions were frequently mentioned. Several previous studies also indicate that employability skills are very amenable to be taught during the undergraduate degree programme (such as Cox and King, 2006; NSF, n.d.; Pool and Sewell, 2007; Rae, 2007; Zinser, 2003). However, exactly where in the curriculum these skills are included and how to impart the skills are beyond the scope of this study. It was also found that universities use industry placements as a method to address employability skills. The extant literature (such as Ball, 2003; Davis 2000) also highlights the importance of a partnership between the

university and industry in providing work experience that complements the programme of study to develop relevant skills at the undergraduate level. Though the extant literature highlights the importance of getting employers involved in the design, delivery and assessment of courses (see Cox and King, 2006; Hegarty and Johnston, 2008; NSF, n.d.), those were not very popular among universities and employers in our sample.

Overall, this article contributes to the investigation of graduate employability skills from the point of view of three main groups- graduates, university lecturers and employers. The software and computer services industry requires employees to possess individual creativity, essential skills and talent for the competitiveness and growth of the industry. When graduates are equipped with necessary skills they will become motivated and efficient in fulfilling their job tasks, and consequently employment retention will be increased. The possession of employability skills by graduates is essentially manifested in priorities given and steps taken by graduates and university lecturers during the undergraduate degree programmes, and by employers in selecting graduates for entry-level graduate jobs and imparting skills in graduates after hiring. When looking ahead to the results as its implications for practice, the findings of this study could be used to assist in universities, graduates, employers, and career advisors to apply strategic decisions in managing graduates' careers. Further, it could be expected that the findings of this study will be able to establish baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Finally, some limitations of this study, however, should be acknowledged. This study relied on individuals' self assessment of skills. It could be assumed that some individuals would consistently give higher (or lower) estimates of the importance of the skills as well as higher (or lower) estimates of their own skill levels. Therefore, future studies could overcome this limitation by employing multiple sources of data, for example derived from

interviews and secondary data. Another limitation of this study is that skills were defined simply, as a headline plus a few sample behaviours: definitions used in this study do not cater for multiple levels of detail and mastery. However, the way skills will be defined will depend on how those will be used and on the purpose of the study. Furthermore, the size of the samples was small and did not allow us to compare the responses of graduates and university lecturers from different universities. With regard to specific areas for future research, it would be interesting to investigate why in some cases the graduates' self-evaluation of their skills exceeded the expectation of employers, especially among female graduates. Further, future studies could relate the actions taken by universities to impart skills in students during the undergraduate degree programme to the students' perceived level of skills. Finally, employability skills of graduates are not just about what graduates have to offer in terms of their degree subject, personal attributes, skills, values and aspirations. It is a learning process. It could be influenced by external factors, such as the economy, trends in the workplace, and cultural orientation. Therefore, it would be possible that Sri Lankan graduates, university lecturers and employers see different skills as more important than do people in other parts of the world. However, as this study is confined to a small sample and also confined to a specific area of study and employment, detailed comparisons between our findings and findings from more developed economies is, therefore, beyond the scope of this study. These all open the door for future investigations.

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Tables

Table I. Comparison of importance given to employability skills (1st five)

Rank	Graduate		Employer	University lecturers
	Male	Female		
1	Learning skills (H)	Self confidence (A)	Problem solving (H)	Working as a team member (A)
2	Problem solving (H)	Learning skills (H)	Positive attitude towards work (A)	Problem solving (H)
3	Self confidence (A)	Problem solving (H)	Working as a team member (A)	Oral communication (B)
4	Working as a team member (A)	Working as a team member (A)	Learning skills (H)	Self confidence (A)
5	Creative and innovative thinking (H)	Positive attitude towards work (A)	Self confidence (A)	Positive attitude towards work (A)

Note. Rank is based on mean values. B= Basic skills; H= Higher order thinking skills; A= Affective skills and traits.

Table II. Importance given to employability skills and differences

Employability skill	Male Graduate <i>Mean</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Female Graduate <i>Mean</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Employer <i>Mean</i> (<i>SD</i>)	University lecturers <i>Mean</i> (<i>SD</i>)	F	Sig.	Partial η^2
Oral communication	4.24 (.74)	4.11 (.78)	3.85 (.71)	4.32 (.72)	2.371	.065	.168
Writing	3.64 (.85)	3.78 (.97)	3.73 (.66)	4.00 (.75)	.981	.405	.029
Reading	4.09 (.73)	4.11 (1.05)	3.85 (.46)	4.18 (.73)	1.039	.379	.031
Basic arithmetic	3.71 (.89)	4.01 (.78)	3.96 (.72)	4.16 (.79)	1.889	.136	.055
Problem solving	4.44 (.65)	4.78 (.44)	4.42 (.50)	4.32 (.56)	1.316	.273	.039
Creative and innovative thinking	4.36 (.64)	4.41 (.92)	4.12 (.71)	4.27 (.76)	.751	.524	.022
Learning skills	4.49 (.50)	4.78 (.28)	4.31 (.54)	3.95 (.57)	8.529	.000***	.207
Decision making	3.87 (.84)	4.33 (.70)	3.77 (.65)	4.00 (.69)	1.399	.248	.041
Responsibility/dependability	4.16 (.70)	4.22 (.44)	4.12 (.74)	4.18 (.79)	.064	.979	.002
Positive attitude towards work	4.31 (.63)	4.67 (.50)	4.38 (.63)	4.11 (.85)	1.156	.330	.034
Working as a team member	4.40 (.72)	4.67 (.49)	4.35 (.68)	4.36 (.79)	.488	.691	.015
Punctuality	3.76 (1.01)	4.12 (.66)	3.88 (.51)	4.09 (.92)	1.21	.310	.036
Self confidence	4.42 (.62)	4.89 (.33)	4.19 (.69)	4.18 (.90)	2.850	.031*	.180
Ability to work without supervision	3.96 (.70)	4.13 (.92)	4.12 (.58)	3.95 (.72)	.393	.759	.012
Adaptability/flexibility	3.96 (.67)	4.00 (.86)	3.99 (.71)	3.82 (.73)	.704	.552	.012

Note. * $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.001$

Table III. Correlations

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
1. Gender	1														
2. Oral communication	-.067	1													
3. Writing	.058	.321*	1												
4. Reading	.011	.126	.573**	1											
5. Basic arithmetic	.170	.364**	.221	.139	1										
6. Problem solving	.197	.040	.307*	.208	.302*	1									
7. Creative and innovative thinking	-.132	.263	.520**	.361**	.270*	.575**	1								
8. Learning skills	.300*	-.135	.173	.107	.071	.236	.246	1							
9. Decision making	.211	-.010	.339*	.326*	.265	.551**	.421**	.301*	1						
10. Responsibility/dependability	.038	-.038	.294*	.223	.225	.601**	.455**	.339*	.595**	1					
11. Positive attitude towards work	.215	-.018	.023	.122	.118	.380**	.292*	.355**	.440**	.439**	1				
12. Working as a team member	.145	-.086	.346*	.062	.010	.343*	.174	.200	.469**	.574**	.399*	1			
13. Punctuality	.182	-.105	.337*	.370**	.177	.291*	.276*	.272*	.340*	.542**	.418**	.480**	1		
14. Self confidence	.289*	.167	.322*	.258	.387**	.659**	.425**	.310*	.541**	.584**	.649**	.540**	.499**	1	
15. Ability to work without supervision	.079	.076	.108	.231	-.006	.180	.195	.079	.243	.313*	.261	.238	.180	.231	1
16. Adaptability/flexibility	.024	-.201	.166	-.028	-.075	.085	.218	.382**	.288*	.378**	.292*	.464**	.298*	.267	.509**

Note. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$.

Table IV. Results of paired sample t-test

	Employability skill	Male graduates			Female graduates		
		Mean	t	Sig	Mean	t	Sig
Pair 1	Oral communication - Possessed	3.33	-7.92	.000***	3.44	-5.54	.001***
	Oral communication - Ideal	4.36			4.56		
Pair 2	Reading - Possessed	3.80	-2.03	.048*	3.88	-1.46	.208
	Reading - Ideal	4.00			4.00		
Pair 3	Basic arithmetic - Possessed	4.18	.53	.596	4.33	.31	.760
	Basic arithmetic - Ideal	4.11			4.20		
Pair 4	Writing- Possessed	3.53	-3.50	.001**	3.89	-.28	.782
	Writing- Ideal	3.89			4.00		
Pair 5	Problem solving - Possessed	3.89	-4.85	.000***	3.56	-4.00	.004**
	Problem solving - Ideal	4.51			4.22		
Pair 6	Learning skills - Possessed	4.02	-5.59	.000***	3.89	-2.82	.022*
	Learning skills- Ideal	4.62			4.56		
Pair 7	Creative and innovative thinking - Possessed	3.73	-5.17	.000***	3.44	-3.50	.008**
	Creative and innovative thinking - Ideal	4.36			4.19		
Pair 8	Decision making - Possessed	3.58	-5.15	.000***	3.22	-8.00	.000***
	Decision making - Ideal	4.18			4.11		
Pair 9	Positive attitude towards work - Possessed	4.13	-2.97	.005**	4.00	-2.80	.023*
	Positive attitude towards work - Ideal	4.44			4.78		
Pair 10	Punctuality - Possessed	3.93	-.69	.490	4.33	-.55	.594
	Punctuality - Ideal	4.04			4.44		
Pair 11	Self confidence - Possessed	4.02	-2.73	.009**	3.78	-2.00	.040*
	Self confidence - Ideal	4.33			4.46		
Pair 12	Working as a team member - Possessed	4.09	-1.34	.185	4.12	-2.53	.035*
	Working as a team member - Ideal	4.27			4.56		
Pair 13	Responsibility/dependability - Possessed	3.67	-3.94	.000***	3.89	-1.41	.195
	Responsibility/dependability - Ideal	4.11			4.18		
Pair 14	Ability to work without supervision - Possessed	3.80	-2.11	.041*	3.56	-2.00	.040*
	Ability to work without supervision - Ideal	4.12			4.20		
Pair 15	Adaptability/Flexibility - Possessed	3.82	-3.08	.004**	3.66	-.88	.403
	Adaptability/Flexibility - Ideal	4.27			4.10		

Note. * p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001, Standard deviations ranged from .67 to 1.02.

Table V. Level of skills expected by employer and the level possessed by graduates at the time of hiring

Employability skill	Male Graduate-possessed <i>Mean (SD)</i>	Female Graduate-possessed <i>Mean (SD)</i>	Employer-expectation <i>Mean (SD)</i>	F	Sig.	Partial η^2
Oral communication	3.33 (.92)	3.44 (.52)	3.69 (.61)	1.646	.200	.041
Writing	3.53 (.75)	3.89 (.60)	3.54 (.81)	.864	.426	.022
Reading	3.80 (.62)	3.88 (.70)	3.73 (.66)	.577	.564	.015
Basic arithmetic	4.18 (.88)	4.33 (.86)	3.85 (.73)	1.730	.184	.043
Problem solving	3.89 (.80)	3.56 (.52)	4.27 (.45)	4.485	.014*	.104
Creative and innovative thinking	3.73 (.83)	3.44 (.52)	4.00 (.69)	2.023	.139	.050
Learning skills	4.02 (.69)	3.89 (.78)	4.51 (.61)	.599	.552	.015
Decision making	3.58 (.78)	3.22 (.44)	3.69 (.67)	1.420	.248	.036
Responsibility/dependability	3.67 (1.0)	3.89 (1.05)	3.85 (.83)	.398	.673	.010
Positive attitude towards work	4.13 (.78)	4.00 (.86)	4.12 (.76)	.108	.898	.003
Working as a team member	4.09 (.82)	4.12 (.60)	4.08 (.74)	.007	.993	.001
Punctuality	3.93 (1.05)	4.33 (.70)	3.69 (.61)	1.76	.178	.044
Self confidence	4.02 (.78)	3.78 (.83)	4.12 (.58)	.713	.493	.018
Ability to work without supervision	3.80 (.75)	3.56 (1.23)	4.08 (.56)	1.887	.158	.047
Adaptability/flexibility	3.82 (.86)	3.66 (.72)	4.15 (.61)	2.031	.138	.050

Note. * $p < 0.05$

Table VI. Measures taken by graduates (% of responses)

Measure	Total	Male	Female
Properly prepared CV	72.2	73.3	66.7
Attending training courses using own funds	27.8	28.9	22.2
University job fairs	16.7	20.0	98.0
Register with job centres	9.3	6.7	24.0

Note. Percentages do not add up to 100 due to multiple responses

Table VII. Measures taken by universities and employers (% of responses)

	% of responses
Universities	
Curriculum revisions	92.6
Organising industry related lecture series	70.4
Organising job fairs with the help of industry participation	63.0
Industry placement	59.3
Workshops	48.1
Mock interviews/tests	33.3
Organizing university industry consultative sessions	12.6
Employer	
Sponsoring training after hiring	88.5
Hosting employer events in universities	38.5
Participating in university industry consultative sessions	15.4

Note. Percentages do not add up to 100 due to multiple responses